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STUDY OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT POLICIES AND KNOWLEDGE SHARING IN SOFTWARE INDUSTRIES

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Abstract:

The process which deals with obtaining, processing, storing, disseminating and applying of information and knowledge within an organization to support and enhance its business performance and employee satisfaction is referred to as Knowledge Management (KM). The main aim of this study is to measure the importance of knowledge management policies and knowledge sharing in software industries. In this study, a sample of 140 respondents was selected randomly from different software companies.

The result clearly shows that components of KM policies and knowledge sharing have positive relation with the organizational performance measured in terms of employee satisfaction.

Keywords: software industries, knowledge management policies, knowledge sharing, Employee Satisfaction

1. Introduction

Knowledge & Knowledge Management Knowledge is defined by the Oxford English Dictionary as (i) expertise, and skills acquired by a person through experience or education; (ii) the theoretical or practical understanding of a subject, (iii) what is known in a particular field and (iv) awareness or familiarity gained by experience of a fact or situation.

Knowledge Management helps to improve the overall organizational performance. Active and dynamic implementation and management of knowledge are the two critical ways of enabling organizational performance enhancements, problem solving and decision making (Liebowitz, 1999).

Knowledge is often defined as a “justified personal belief.” There are much taxonomy that specify various kinds of knowledge. The most fundamental distinction is between “tacit” and “explicit” knowledge. (King, 2009)

The Knowledge Management Policy sets the standard for Knowledge Management within an organisation. It ensures that everyone knows what is expected of them in terms of Knowledge Management, and why this is important to the organisation.

Knowledge sharing is a process through which knowledge is exchanged among people and members of an organization.

Employee Satisfaction refers to the attitude of an employee towards his work and organizational environment. Each employee has a different level of satisfaction in accordance with the system of values prevailing itself, because each employee has a wide range of perceptions of job satisfaction itself. Employee satisfaction concerns with a person's attitude

This study is an attempt to find the importance of knowledge management policies and knowledge sharing in knowledge management.

2. Literature Review:

Hurley, et. al. (2005) in their paper offers many suggestions to Non-governmental organizations NGOs for more effectively managing their knowledge. Leavitt's model of organization change is reviewed and suggested as a framework for NGOs to consider in their development and implementation of a "within" KM program. This model suggests that in order to affect change, a coordinated effort of adjustment and balance between technology, people, task, and structure is required. More specifically, the model suggests that the addition of technology alone is not sufficient. Instead, all four of the subsystems require balance in order for a KM culture to be successfully established.

Aurum et.al., (2007) in their study, using both quantitative and qualitative methods, investigates current practice of Knowledge Management (KM) in Software Engineering (SE) processes in two Australian companies on the basis that they both claimed to apply KM practices in their software development work. It also describes the KM activities and KM process used in SE practice, and examines the enablers of KM process for SE in terms of leadership, technology, culture, process and measurement.

Technol. *et. al.* (2013), in the article states that for Knowledge Management to be efficient and effective, some principles should be considered (Davenport and Prusak, 2003): a) Knowledge originates and resides in people's heads; b) Knowledge-sharing requires trust; c) Technology enables new behaviors related to knowledge; d) Knowledge sharing should be encouraged and rewarded; e) Support of the leadership and resources are essential factors; f) Initiatives related to knowledge should begin with a pilot program; g) Quantitative and qualitative measurements are necessary to evaluate the initiative; h) Knowledge is creative and should be encouraged to develop in unexpected ways.

Howell and Annansingh (2013) investigated whether there was any path-dependency in association

with cultural expectations of knowledge generation and sharing in knowledge intensive firms.

They

concluded that certain universities display critical junctures and cultural transformation in terms of

knowledge generation, dissemination and sharing.

Jiacheng et al. (2010) reported that intrinsic motivation operated through affective commitment: internalization, identification and conformity; rewards had little direct impacts on final intentions. They explored individual cognitive mechanisms of knowledge-sharing (KS) motivation to provide effective measures of individual inclinations towards KS.

Alhawari et al. (2012) presented a knowledge-based risk management framework for information technology project. They explored the field of risk management associated with KM and attempted to present a conceptual framework, called Knowledge-Based Risk Management (KBRM), which employed KM processes to improve its effectiveness and to increase the likelihood of success in

innovative Information Technology (IT) projects.

3. Objectives of the Research

The aim of this research is to study the effectiveness of knowledge management in software industries by analysing the influences of different dimensions of knowledge management policies and organisational effectiveness. To accomplish this aim, following objectives have been developed.

1. Identify the dimensions which constitute the knowledge sharing and employee satisfaction as relevant to effectiveness of knowledge management in the organization.
2. Develop a metric to measure above mentioned research constructs and validate it.
3. Obtain the empirical evidence for the inter-relationships between the dimensions of the research constructs.

Draw implications and make suggestions to the organizations to enhance the organizational performance by implementing knowledge management effectively and efficiently.

4. Methodology

The questionnaire on the two dimensions namely Knowledge Management policies and knowledge sharing of knowledge management (having 7 and 9 questions respectively) is prepared and distributed in Google Forms to the employees of different software companies. 141 employees from different software industries responded to the questionnaire. The questionnaire had 13 a priori items on a Likert 5-point scale (5-strongly agree and 1-Strongly disagree).

Likert Scale is a psychometric scale, which is one of the most widely used question types in a survey. In a Likert Scale Survey respondents has specific choices based on "agreeing" or "disagreeing" on a certain question in the survey rather than simply choosing between "yes/no"

Likert scale survey questions are useful in measuring respondent's opinion or attitude towards a given subject. Likert Scale is typically a five, seven, or nine point agreement scale used to measure respondents' agreement with a variety of statements. In this study a five point scale is used for measuring respondent's response.

This study tests only one main hypothesis (the role of knowledge management policies and knowledge sharing in effectiveness of knowledge management).

Total responses for each category is tabulated, analyzed and graph is prepared to show the importance of each of the factors in the knowledge management

5. Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant effect of knowledge management policies on employee satisfaction of software industries.

H1: There a significant effect of knowledge management policies on employee satisfaction of software industries.

H0: There is no significant effect of knowledge sharing on employee satisfaction of software industries.

H1: There a significant effect of knowledge sharing on employee satisfaction of software industries.

Results and Analysis

KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT POLICIES							
	KMP1	KMP2	KMP3	KMP4	KMP5	KMP6	KMP7
Strongly disagree	3	1	2	1	2	2	2
Disagree	3	10	8	7	10	4	8
Neutral	22	24	26	34	25	17	19
Agree	76	77	77	71	79	90	71
Strongly agree	37	29	28	28	25	28	41

Table 1.1: Total responses in 5 point scale to different items related to Knowledge Management policies

- KMP1 - There is a Knowledge Management methodology or set of plans in our Organization for acquiring and sharing Knowledge.
- KMP2 - There is an advisory board and internal meetings are held by our organization to exchange Knowledge.
- KMP3 - Our Organization encourages systematic neighbour training and interdisciplinary training groups in order to get holistic overview of a given task.
- KMP4 - Knowledge sharing is prompted most effectively and it is incorporated in the Organization’s strategic activities.
- KMP5 - There is support and trust for Knowledge Management policy formulation in our Organization.
- KMP6 - Employees accept the activities designed to acquire and share knowledge as part of their job.
- KMP7 - Meetings are also used as a means of transferring Knowledge in our Organization.

	Strongly disagree (%)	Disagree(%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly agree (%)
KMP1	2%	2%	16%	54%	26%
KMP2	1%	7%	17%	55%	21%
KMP3	1%	6%	18%	55%	20%
KMP4	1%	5%	24%	50%	20%
KMP5	1%	7%	18%	56%	18%
KMP6	1%	3%	12%	64%	20%
KMP7	1%	6%	13%	50%	29%

Table 1.2 : Average responses to different items used to measure Knowledge Management Policies with 5 point scale.

Figure 1.1: Graphical representation of responses for each items related to Knowledge Management Policies with 5 point scale.

Out of 141 responses 77% (55% Agree and 22% Strongly Agree) of the employees have accepted that they have effective Knowledge Management policies in their organizations, only 6% (1% Strongly disagree and 5% Disagree) have denied that they have effective knowledge management policies, 17% neither agree or disagree for the fact by being neutral.

KNOWLEDGE SHARING									
	KSH1	KSH2	KSH3	KSH4	KSH5	KSH6	KSH7	KSH8	KSH9
Strongly disagree	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	2	3
Disagree	8	14	6	13	13	10	11	15	11
Neutral	28	20	17	31	26	33	26	29	22
Agree	72	77	83	67	80	75	83	74	82
Strongly agree	32	29	34	27	21	21	19	20	22

Table 1.3: Shows the total responses in 5 point scale to different items related to Knowledge Sharing

- KSH1 - Senior officials and staff share their experiences and advice through Knowledge Management practices.
- KSH2 - New employees are encouraged to use knowledge portal and knowledge bank to learn how things are done.
- KSH3 - Sharing best practices help employees to provide useful feedback that helps to increase learning.
- KSH4 - It is easy to browse Knowledge bank in this organization.
- KSH5 - Knowledge Management portals are used to coordinate with other teams to meet organizational objectives.
- KSH6 - Knowledge Gaps are systematically identified and well-defined processes are used to bridge the knowledge gaps.
- KSH7 - The organization has formalized the process of transferring best practices, including documentation and lessons learned to other departments.

- KSH8 - Tacit knowledge (what employees know how to do, but cannot express) is valued and transferred across the organization.
- KSH9 - Knowledge bank is regularly used to figure out ways to improve the work processes

	Strongly disagree (%)	Disagree(%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly agree (%)
KSH1	0%	6%	20%	51%	23%
KSH2	0%	10%	14%	55%	21%
KSH3	0%	4%	12%	59%	24%
KSH4	1%	9%	22%	48%	19%
KSH5	0%	9%	19%	57%	15%
KSH6	1%	7%	24%	54%	15%
KSH7	0%	8%	19%	59%	14%
KSH8	1%	11%	21%	53%	14%
KSH9	2%	8%	16%	59%	16%

Table 1.4: Average responses to different items used to measure Knowledge Sharing with 5 point scale.

Figure 1.2: Graphical representation of responses for each items related to Knowledge Sharing with 5 point scale.

Out of 141 responses 73% (55% Agree and 18% Strongly Agree) of the employees have accepted that they have effectiveness in their organizations, only 9% (1% Strongly disagree and 8% Disagree) have denied that they have effective knowledge Sharing , 18% neither agree or disagree for the fact by being neutral.

EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION					
	EMS1	EMS2	EMS3	EMS4	EMS5
Strongly disagree	2	7	7	5	4
Disagree	6	12	14	9	7
Neutral	28	26	27	34	41
Agree	77	73	73	69	65
Strongly agree	27	22	19	23	23

Table 1.5: Shows the total responses in 5 point scale to different items related to Employee Satisfaction.

- EMS1 - Our organization improves working conditions in order to recognize the quality improvement efforts of employees
- EMS2 - Our organization has an incentive scheme for encouraging employee participation in quality improvement.
- EMS3 - The organization offers incentives to its employees relative to their performance.
- EMS4 - Employees' reward and penalties are clear to all.
- EMS5 - Compensation and reward in the organization is in par with others in the business.

	Strongly disagree (%)	Disagree(%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly agree (%)
EMS1	1%	4%	20%	55%	19%
EMS2	5%	9%	19%	52%	16%
EMS3	5%	10%	19%	52%	14%
EMS4	4%	6%	24%	48%	16%
EMS5	3%	5%	29%	46%	16%

Table 1.6: Average responses to different items used to measure Employee Satisfaction with 5 point scale.

Figure 1.3: Graphical representation of responses for each items related to Employee Satisfaction with 5 point scale.

Out of 141 responses 62% (46% Agree and 16% Strongly Agree) of the employees have accepted that they have effectiveness in their organizations, only 8% (3% Strongly disagree

and 5% Disagree) have denied that they have effective employee satisfaction in Knowledge Management, 29% neither agree or disagree for the fact by being neutral.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the study

Total of 141 responses were collected from different employees by distribution of questionnaire.

Out of 141 responses 77% of the employees have accepted that they have Knowledge Management policies (KMP) in their organizations and 74% accepted that they have knowledge sharing (KSH) methods in their organizations.

	KMP	KSH	EMS
Strongly disagree (%)	1%	1%	4%
Disagree (%)	5%	6%	7%
Neutral (%)	17%	19%	23%
Agree (%)	55%	56%	49%
Strongly agree (%)	22%	18%	17%

6. Conclusion

The result shows that more than 75% of employees agreed that they have Knowledge Management Policies and Knowledge Sharing is the two important concepts adopted in their organizations. So this proves that these two concepts of knowledge management are very effective tools and this is true with regard to the alternative hypothesis. Good implementation of Knowledge Management Policies and Knowledge Sharing shows the high rate of employee satisfaction.

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